

THE PROBLEM OF PROFESSIONAL AND MENTAL HEALTH IN PSYCHOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the issue of occupational health and mental stability in psychology from a scientific and theoretical point of view. Based on approaches in Western psychology and national psychological traditions of Uzbekistan, the essence, factors and psychoprophylactic directions of occupational mental health are highlighted. Also, occupational stress, burnout syndrome and mechanisms for their elimination are analyzed

In modern psychology, the mental and professional health of a person is one of the most pressing issues. A person actively uses not only physical, but also mental resources in his work. Therefore, professional balance, emotional stability and mental health are the main psychological conditions for labor productivity. In today's conditions of globalization, competition and increased information pressure, the level of mental stability, stress tolerance and psychological adaptation of specialists determine their professional success.

Occupational health is the harmonious development of a person physically, mentally and socially in the process of his professional activity, the ability to maintain internal resources and adapt to stress factors. Occupational health consists of the following components: emotional stability, motivational readiness, social adaptation and personal self-awareness.

Mental health is a person's internal harmony, immunity to stress and the ability to maintain a positive emotional state. According to the definition of the WHO, mental health is a state of being able to realize one's own potential, manage life's stresses and contribute to society.

In modern international psychology, the issues of occupational health and mental stability have been extensively studied in conceptual areas such as occupational stress, job satisfaction, personality-occupational compatibility, emotional stability, and professional motivation. Scientific approaches to this issue have been widely developed, especially in developed countries such as the USA, Canada, Western Europe, Japan, and South Korea, and the issue is viewed more from the perspective of productivity, preservation of human capital, satisfaction of professional needs, and social stability. One of the most important theories in this area is the concept of "burnout syndrome" developed by Christina Maslach. It describes professional burnout through three main components: emotional exhaustion, personal worthlessness, and professional alienation. The "Professional Burnout" test, created on the basis of this theory, is one of the standard methods used in psychological diagnostics

worldwide, and is widely used, especially in the fields of health care, education, and social services. Maslach's approach is of fundamental importance in terms of identifying the negative consequences of occupational stress and developing psychoprophylactic mechanisms against it.[1]

Another important scientific theory of professional activity is the "Self-regulation Theory" put forward by E. Deci and R. Ryan, which analyzes motivation through internal and external factors. According to this test, mental health is optimally ensured only when a person's internal needs - autonomy (independent decision-making), competence (feeling competent) and relatedness (social integration) - are satisfied during his professional activity. Professional health is strengthened by relying on internal motivation, which is formed on the basis of these needs.[2]

In addition, approaches that take into account the cultural context also play an important role in global psychology. In particular, sociocultural researchers such as G. Hofstede and S. Schwartz have empirically studied the relationship between professional values and mental stability in different cultures. Hofstede, in his famous cultural dimensions model, emphasizes that in collectivist societies (for example, in Eastern countries), professional health is determined more by social appreciation, group belonging, and moral responsibility. On the contrary, in individualistic societies (Western countries), mental health is more closely related to personal freedom, professional independence, and the ability to make one's own choices. Thus, research on professional and mental health in international psychology is multidisciplinary, culturally, regionally, and methodologically rich and complex. These studies show that the profession is not only a form of socio-economic activity, but also one of the central factors determining the psychological state of a person. Also, occupational health is the result of a balance between internal needs, the social environment, and working conditions, the maintenance of which ensures the stability of society and the continuous development of human resource potential.[3]

In the Uzbek school of psychology, mental health is interpreted in relation to spiritual values, moral balance, and spiritual education.

In recent years, issues of occupational health and mental stability have been forming as an independent scientific direction in Uzbek psychology. Research in this area is mainly focused on such important psychological areas as the suitability of a person for a profession, occupational stress, psychological defense mechanisms, motivation for work, professional personality and psychological immunity. These studies expand the practical aspects of national psychology that meet the needs of society and serve to deeply analyze psychological situations in the professional environment. The research of Professor Sayyora Karimova is one of the fundamental works in Uzbek psychology that analyzed the relationship between occupational stress and mental stability. Her research is especially distinguished by the fact that it is aimed at studying the relationship between values, spiritual factors and occupational stress in the minds of young people. According to Karimova, occupational stress is a complex psychological condition that occurs as a result of an imbalance between a person's internal psychological resources and external pressures, working conditions, and social demands. In this approach, stress is not seen as an external factor, but as the result of the conflict between

internal and external forces, which can be interpreted as a localized form of modern stress theories.

Professor S. Karimova proposes the concept of “psychological immunity” as a central concept in maintaining professional health. Psychological immunity is a psychological system based on the internal resources of the individual, providing stress resistance, supporting a stable mental state. Its components include emotional stability, moral principles, religious strength, clarity of life goals, an active social position, and a spiritual attitude to the profession. These components help the individual not only to withstand the difficulties of professional activity, but also to maintain professional stability. S. Karimova pays special attention to the phenomenon of “information stress”, which is becoming increasingly common in modern socio-cultural conditions. In her opinion, the extremely intensive and unbalanced flow of information that is forming in the minds of young people is becoming a factor weakening mental stability. This situation leads to a decrease in the ability to consciously process information, psychological fatigue, fading professional motivation, and loss of internal concentration. Also, the concept of “decline in work motivation” put forward by Karimova is associated with such processes as professional apathy, loss of internal positive interest, and weakening of the sincere need for work among today's youth. This situation can lead to the deterioration of mental health, a decrease in self-esteem, and social isolation. From a scientific point of view, Sayyora Karimova's concept creates a solid theoretical and methodological basis for studying the interrelationship of professional activity and mental stability in Uzbek psychology. The concepts she put forward, in harmony with national values, serve to adapt universal psychological principles to the regional mentality. In particular, the idea of maintaining professional stability by integrating the internal moral position of the individual with mental immunity can serve as an important theoretical approach for the national model of modern labor psychology.[5]

In the study of the problems of occupational health and mental stability in Uzbek psychology, the scientific research of Professor Nodira Davletova occupies a special place. She has especially deeply analyzed personal deformations that occur in the process of professional activity - that is, the fading of personal qualities, distortion of direction or negative changes. Davletova's research specifically highlights the symptoms that arise as a result of prolonged professional stress among specialists working in the pedagogical, medical and law enforcement spheres - "emotional indifference", "apathy", "professional indifference". These conditions are interpreted as a violation of psychological defense mechanisms. Davletova notes that these mechanisms are natural protective resources of a person aimed at maintaining internal stability in relation to external psychogenic factors. If these mechanisms fail as a result of working in an environment of excessive load, emotional exhaustion or underestimation for a long time, the person's internal motivation decreases, apathy towards work increases, and mental stress occurs.

Davletova analyzes professional deformation in three stages: the first is emotional exhaustion, the second is depersonalization (abandonment of a personal approach to people), and the third is a low assessment of professional achievements. These stages correspond to the internal components of the "professional burnout syndrome" model in modern psychology. According to her, this syndrome directly threatens the mental health of an

individual, reduces the ability to perform professional activities, weakens social activity, and leads to the breakdown of communicative relations in the team. Professor Davletova emphasizes the need for professional reflection, mental hygiene, regular psychological monitoring, reassessment of the personal approach to work, restoration of personal resources, and improvement of the psychological climate to prevent these negative situations. These factors are especially important for employees in the medical and pedagogical fields to maintain the effectiveness of life and professional activities.[6]

Her scientific research not only enriches the field of occupational psychology in Uzbekistan, but also serves to empirically substantiate the deep interrelationship between occupational health and mental stability.

Occupational health and mental stability are one of the important areas of integrated study in Uzbek psychology, and the research conducted by Professor Shahodat Rahmatullayeva in this area deserves special scientific attention. In particular, she puts forward the process of a person's self-realization through professional activity as a basic psychological principle. Rahmatullayeva interprets the profession not only as a means of material support, but also as a means of personal growth, spiritual elevation, and social appreciation in society. From this point of view, professional activity plays an important role in the formation of a person's psychological identity. In her research, Rahmatullayeva highlights several factors as the main psychological determinants that ensure mental stability. In her opinion, mental stability is determined, first of all, by a person's internal satisfaction with his work. Feeling useful in professional activities, satisfaction with work results, provides emotional balance in a person, and this condition serves to strengthen overall mental health. In addition, Rahmatullayeva sees the level of self-esteem of a person as one of the criteria for mental stability. How a person assesses his abilities, professional potential and social role directly affects his internal mental state. Also, in order to ensure strong mental health in a professional environment, a person's self-confidence — that is, the confidence to make independent decisions, take initiative and realize his potential — is an extremely important psychological resource. Another important factor that Rahmatullayeva emphasizes is the presence of a social support system. When a person feels constant emotional, spiritual and practical support from team members, leaders or family members in their professional activities, they perceive themselves as a valued and needed person. This, in turn, is one of the main social factors that strengthen mental stability. Shahodat Rahmatullayeva paid special attention to the empirical study of professional health and mental stability, especially among professionals working in the social sphere - teachers, psychologists, medical workers and social service specialists. In her research, a person's professional motivation, job satisfaction, level of self-awareness and feelings of social appreciation were analyzed as central criteria for stable mental health. The approaches put forward by Shahodat Rahmatullayeva create a scientific and practical basis in national psychology aimed at strengthening professional identity, activating internal resources and creating a healthy work environment. According to his views, a profession is a key tool for a person to realize themselves, determine their place in society, and achieve spiritual well-being.[7]

Within the framework of Uzbek psychology, research on the problems of occupational health and mental stability has its own methodological and substantive characteristics. First

of all, scientific developments in this area are mainly carried out based on empirical observations, psychodiagnostic methods and statistical analysis. This allows us to identify psychological concepts based on practical experiences, in addition to theoretical approaches. Secondly, in local studies, the concept of mental health is often interpreted in an integrated manner with moral and spiritual values. There is a tendency to associate mental stability not only with an emotional state or mental strength, but also with a person's moral position, spiritual motives and internal belief system. This aspect is especially evident in studies conducted taking into account the national mentality and cultural context. Thirdly, in Uzbek psychology, such problems as occupational stress, emotional exhaustion, motivational decline, and mental fatigue are being analyzed in depth. Due to the widespread occurrence of these conditions, especially among professionals related to social activities (teachers, doctors, law enforcement officers), the issues of psychoprophylaxis and the formation of mental immunity have been formed as a priority area. Fourth, in the psychological thinking of Uzbekistan, values such as patience, honesty, faith, responsibility, inherent in Eastern traditions, are inextricably linked with psychological concepts. These values are interpreted as the main means of strengthening mental stability, social adaptability and internal discipline in professional activities. As a result, a unique model of professional health is being formed in the national school of psychology - this model, along with having a scientific and empirical basis, is also combined with cultural and traditional factors. In this model, a person's mental health is considered together with satisfaction in professional activities, social appreciation and spiritual growth. This serves to form an integrative approach aimed at ensuring professional well-being based on the combination of modern psychology and Eastern philosophy.

Occupational stress is a state of mental tension arising from the imbalance between a person's own capabilities and external demands in working conditions. The "burnout" syndrome is characterized by emotional exhaustion, apathy and alienation from professional work.

Professional and mental health is an important psychological factor that determines not only a person's work efficiency, but also the quality of life. Preventing occupational stress, developing mental resources and forming positive motivation ensure a person's professional stability.

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